

RETROSPECTIVE STUDY ON INTERNAL PARASITISM OF SHEEP IN THE EAST OF ALGERIA

HADJAB Naima⁽¹⁾, ALLAOUI Assia^{(1) (2)}, BELKACEM Lilia⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Laboratory ESPA ISVSA-University Hadj Lakhdar Batna1. Algeria.

⁽²⁾ Laboratory GSPA. Institute of Veterinary Sciences, University of Constantine1. Algeria.

Özet

Cezayir'de koyun çiftliği hayvan üretiminin en önemli alt sektörü olarak kabul ediliyor. Özellikle çeşitliliğe ve çiftliklerin davranış modlarına uyum sağlama niteliklerinin önemine bağlı olarak çok güçlü bir potansiyele sahiptir. Ancak iç kısımdaki sıkıntılar, ürünün kalitesini önemli bir ekonomik konuma sahip olacak şekilde düşüren engellerden biri. Bu çalışmanın başlıca amacı, Est Cezayir'de bulunan Khenchela'nın belandaki koyunda en yaygın gastrointestinal parazitleri bilmek ve üreyene yönelik nöbet ve ekonomik etkilerini azaltmak için üreme konusunda olası önleyici önlemleri belirlemektir. 2021 yılı boyunca wilaya de Khenchela Veterinerlik Muayenesi veterinerleri tarafından toplam 8782 koyun kargası ovoidan sonra incelemeye tabi tutuldu. Sonuç, öldürülen hayvanların 11.85%'inin baskın ile birlikte iç parazitize ortaya koyduğunu gösteren *Échinococcuse granulosis* (92.69%), ardından *Fasciola hepatica* (5.76%), 1.53%'inin ise bakteriyel hastalık tüberküloz nedeniyle ele geçirildiği ortaya çıktı. Bu nedenle, pulmoner sistlerin istila hızının sırasıyla 100% ve 32.22% ile hepatik oranından yüksek olduğunu belirttik. Bu sonuçlara göre, bira edenlerinin parazit enfeksiyonlarını kontrol etmek için uygun profilksisi takip etmesi gerekir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Cezayir; koyun; iç parantez

Abstract

In Algeria, sheep farming is considered the most important sub-sector of animal production. It is characterized by very strong potential, due in particular to the diversity and the importance of its qualities of adaptation to the modes of conduct of the farms. However internal parasitizes are one of those obstacles that reduce the quality of the product to have an important economic position. The main objective of this study is to know the most common gastrointestinal parasites in sheep in the wilaya of Khenchela situated in the Est Algerian and identify possible preventive measures in breeding to reduce seizures and their economic impacts for the breeder. A total of 8782 sheep carcasses were subject to post-mortem inspection by the veterinarians of the Veterinary Inspection of the wilaya de Khenchela during the year 2021. The result showed that 11.85% of slaughtered animals presented internal parasitize with the dominant is *Échinococcuse granulosis* (92.69%) followed by *Fasciola hepatica* (5.76%), while 1.53% are seized because of bacterial disease tuberculosis. Thereby, we noted that the infestation rate of pulmonary cysts was higher than that of hepatic with 100% and 32.22 respectively. Based on these results, breeders should follow proper prophylaxis to control parasitic infections.

Key words; Algeria; Sheep; internal parasitize

1. INTRODUCTION

In Algeria, the hydatid cyst is a parasitic disease and a major medical and veterinary problem, due to their impact on public health or economic (Kamal Brik et al., 2018). Indeed, the parasitic cycle takes place between the dog, the definitive host, and the herbivore mammals (cattle, sheep, and goats) which would explain the endemicity of the parasitosis in some countries (North Africa, Mediterranean basin, Eastern Europe); with the possibility of accidental insertion of man into the cycle ([Deplazes et al., 2017](#)).

Clinical diagnosis of animal hydatidosis is almost impossible; the disease is the subject of a discovery of slaughterhouses. Veterinary seizures carried out to guarantee food safety are a potential source of information to detect the most dominant parasitic diseases on farms and to allow the implementation of corrective measures. Through this approach our work aims to determine the nature and frequency of the different reasons for seizures of red offal in sheep and identify the different types of parasites to learn about possible preventive measures.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Our study took place over a period of one year (2021) during which a total of 8,782 sheep carcasses were subject to post-mortem inspection by veterinarians of the Veterinary Inspection of the wilaya de kenchela (which is located in eastern Algeria).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study of the reasons for the seizure has thus become an alert witness; it makes it possible to detect quickly a problem within the farm. Data presented in the first figure shown that **11.85%** of slaughtered animals presented internal parasitization with the dominant is *Échinococcuse granulosus* (**92.69%**) followed by *Fasciola hepatica* (**5.76%**), while 1.53% are seized because of bacterial disease tuberculosis. The highest level unregistered four hydatidic cysts indicate the life cycle of the cestode between the sheep and the dog is still exist, despite the attempts to control the slaughter and the intensification of extension campaigns to stop their spread. Moreover, we noted that the infestation rate of pulmonary cysts was higher than that of hepatic with 100% and 32.22 respectively (figure 2).

Figure 1: prevalence of affected animals

Figure 2: prevalence of the mains causes of seizures of lung and liver in sheep

4. CONCLUSION

The regional data obtained indicate that the reasons for seizures lead to considerable losses of animal protein and that the high prevalence of echinococcosis should be considered as indicative of a rural cycle that requires the application of surveillance to limit human infestation and economic loss.

5. REFERENCE

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